

SYSTEM OF FORMING A POSITIVE WORLD VIEW IN STUDENTS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL TEACHINGS

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Abstract: This thesis examines the problem of forming a positive outlook in the modern education system. Also studied the interdependence of the principles of a holistic positive worldview and the principles of the educational and educational process in the structure of higher education.

Key words: positivity, educational system, higher education, positive outlook, teaching.

Introduction.

Currently, the development of Uzbekistan is determined by its market economy, its integration into the world community with the European educational space, the need to eliminate the country's lagging behind the global trends of economic and social development. In solving these problems, education is the most important factor in forming a new quality of human capital, its ability to create the best examples of the world in science, economy, culture, and the role of the country, which ensures the ability of the country to compete with the advanced countries of the world, will increase significantly. Improving the quality of the education system in our country is currently related to its comprehensive modernization.

The conceptual ideas of higher education reform are to strengthen the individualization and socialization of students through a flexible and changing system of multi-level education. In the new conditions of Uzbekistan's socio-economic development, the role of the ability to plan and implement one's life strategy is increasing, based on the conditions of adequate assessment of one's own capabilities and self-awareness in society. For the active life of a growing person, it is necessary to have a positive and stable motivation, his desire for achievements in creative, work, creative activities, and a desire for success in life on a moral and legal basis. The school is called as an active social institution to solve the new problems faced by the modern society.

The modern education model is a new school of educational quality, a school of high achievement and achievement for every teacher and every student. It is a cultural and educational center that forms a socio-cultural educational environment in the surrounding society. The goal of education is to achieve a high level of social maturity of the graduate, his readiness for constant

changes in independent life in society, the ability to make responsible decisions in the conditions of selection, vocational training for the benefit of the individual and the state, spiritual and moral improvement and responsibility for the fate of the country. The meaning of education is education for a new quality of life. The model of a modern school graduate is one with clear moral orientations, basic competences and competences for continuing education, self-awareness and adaptation, for a creative lifestyle in the changing conditions of the 21st century. a knowledgeable person who is ready. Formation of social, moral and aesthetic relations in students. A more generalized and highest level of a person's relationship to the world around him and an effective regulator of his behavior and activity is worldview. It acts as a decisive factor in the personal development and formation of a person. Therefore, the issues of forming the worldview of students is the most important educational task of the school.

It is necessary to understand in more detail what role worldview plays in human life and behavior and why it is the most important topic of school education. Many examples and facts from the lives of famous people show that worldview not only effectively affects the spiritual and moral development of a person, but also helps him to show determination and courage in various life conditions, difficulties and difficulties. The orientation-regulating function of worldview is related to the fact that a person's behavior and activities are determined by his consciousness, views and beliefs. If a person has formed this or that worldview, developed stable views and beliefs, then they, as a rule, determine his actions and actions. The evaluation function of the worldview is related to the fact that a person evaluates all the events of life around him based on his views and beliefs, or in other words, his worldview.

A positive worldview in this context works as a system of views, principles, values and beliefs that define a person's positive attitude towards the surrounding reality, describe a positive vision of the whole world and their place in it. A positive attitude towards this system and the reality it defines is the level of thinking of a person, as an indirect and generalized reflection of this reality, the type of mental activity of a person, knowing the essence of things and events, the natural connections and relationships between them, and it is this level of thinking - his it is formed by its orientation towards goodness and creativity. Only a person with a positive outlook determined by positive thinking and high spiritual and moral potential can go through the difficult years of crisis trials without losing. Consequently, a positive level of thinking is not only a condition

for a positive outlook of a person, but also begins to act as a means of combating a crisis in a negative environment.

Currently, educational institutions are entrusted with the task of not only imparting knowledge, skills and professional experience to the young generation of specialists, but also adapting them to the complex modern conditions of practical activity - educating positive thinking against the crisis, which determines the positive outlook of the future specialist. In addition, in this context, the main educational role is assigned to the teacher who directly implements the educational process. This teacher, first of all, should inculcate the basics of positive thinking: not only to convey a certain amount of knowledge and skills, to develop a certain amount of skills, but most importantly - necessary for full cognitive creative activity. formation of motivation and psychological basis, development of mental qualities of the student necessary for this, positive emotional level of perception of the world around him, development of creative will, diligence and self-confidence, mechanical method of acquiring knowledge. turning this knowledge into a principle of meaningful perception, integration and demonstration in activity, etc.

Such a worldview allows for the optimal implementation of life activities and helps to develop an unlimited way of life and achieve wisdom. But the main purpose of using a worldview in the stage of targeted development is to develop a character that affirms a holistic life. If we translate the worldview problem from the field of philosophy to the field of pedagogy, it can be formulated as follows: what should be the worldview of a modern student (that is, what should be educated) and how should this worldview be formed (how to educate). Modern pedagogy answers personal questions: moral values, value orientations, etc., but the issue of forming a holistic worldview has not yet been resolved.

Summary.

Thus, the optimization of the educational process includes two educational and training directions. At the same time, the importance and role of such an important aspect as psychological is not clearly defined. A complete educational process is possible only in the conditions of the implementation of the principles of a positive worldview. The interdependence of educational, pedagogical and psychological principles is observed more in specialized education. At the same time, the student's opportunities to build an individual educational trajectory are significantly expanded. The educational profile implies the need for choice, that is, the implementation of such a principle of forming a positive worldview as the clarity of the goal. Based on this, at the stage of pre-profile education, the

child and parents should be ready to make a conscious choice, clearly define their educational goals, near and far. When goals are consciously defined, the implementation of principles such as independence and self-management, doing more and better is possible and natural in the learning process. Of course, the educational process is two-way (student-teacher). The role of the teacher as a scientific supervisor, teacher, psychologist is great. Therefore, it is necessary to implement such a principle as cooperation. The task of the teacher is to form the educational process taking into account the development and implementation of the following principles: positive attitude, clear thinking, proper distribution of energy, concentration, imagination and lessons from failures. Educational processes are among the most important processes included in the field of professional pedagogical activity.

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